

2D simulation results with preference of polymer and fullerene at the substrate



3D simulation result with preference of polymer and fulleren at the substrate



2D simulation results with preference of polymer at the substrate



2D simulation result with weaker preference of polymer at the substrate



2D simulation result with preference of solvent at the substrate

